

1 **Jarid2 has functions in pluripotency.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of Jarid2 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in human embryonic
11 stem cells.

12 Citations

13 1. Pasini, D., Cloos, P.A., Walfridsson, J., Olsson, L., Bukowski, J.P., Johansen, J.V., Bak, M.,
14 Tommerup, N., Rappsilber, J. and Helin, K., 2010. JARID2 regulates binding of the Polycomb repressive
15 complex 2 to target genes in ES cells. *Nature*, 464(7286), pp.306-310.

16 2. Kasinath, V., Beck, C., Sauer, P., Poepsel, S., Kosmatka, J., Faini, M., Toso, D., Aebersold, R. and
17 Nogales, E., 2021. JARID2 and AEBP2 regulate PRC2 in the presence of H2AK119ub1 and other histone
18 modifications. *Science*, 371(6527), p.eabc3393.